

The Branding and Reputation of Islamic Education: Its Impact on Public Perceptions of Islamic Schools, West Java, Indonesia

***Aat Ruchiat Nugraha**

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6501-2553>

Iriana Bakti

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3052-5057>

Feliza Zubair

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8447-3344>

Faculty of Communication Science, Universitas Padjadjaran, Sumedang, Indonesia

*Corresponding author email: ruchiat@unpad.ac.id

Abstract

Background: Islamic schools are educational institutions that carry out the mandate to educate the community and strengthen the nation's character based on Islamic values and principles. In running its education system, Islamic schools rely heavily on funding from the community. Therefore, internal strength is needed in branding and reputation activities to strengthen positive assessments and build community trust, thereby realising national education that produces a bright and characterful generation.

Objective: This study aims to analyse the influence of branding activities, the reputation of Islamic educational institutions, and their impact on public attitudes towards Islamic schools in West Java Province, Indonesia.

Methodology: This study employs a quantitative, non-experimental, hypothetical-deductive approach, utilising a cross-sectional design. The sample consisted of 277 parent respondents from Islamic schools, selected based on predetermined criteria that included the average national exam scores obtained by these schools.

Result: Branding and reputation directly and positively influence 77.4% of the community's attitude towards Islamic schools. The remaining 22.6% is influenced by factors such as emotional closeness, spiritual appeal, educational experience, and information literacy. Emphasis is placed on management continuity in designing and implementing branding and reputation activities of Islamic education institutions to enhance the cohesiveness and loyalty of parents (community).

Conclusions: The branding and reputation of Islamic educational institutions significantly influence public attitudes toward Islamic schools. The better the image and perception of the branding and reputation of academic institutions, the more positive the public attitude towards Islamic schools, which in turn can increase public trust and participation in choosing and supporting these educational institutions.

The unique contribution: This study offers novel empirical evidence by integrating and validating the interplay of branding and reputation within the underexplored context of Islamic education. The work advances theory by providing a robust, empirical analysis of the combined influence of these dual strategic approaches on shaping public attitudes.

Recommendations: Future research is recommended to explore additional factors that may influence the dynamics of branding activities and reputation of both Islamic and general education institutions, and examine the long-term effects of both variables in maintaining community loyalty to Islamic schools.

Keywords: Islamic School; Branding; Reputation; Attitude; Parents of Students

Introduction

Parents need references to enrol their children in quality educational institutions as part of the societal entity. Academic institutions, as entities that produce mass services in education, greatly need quality processes and outputs to become competitive and have bargaining power against other service institutions. Public assessment of the quality of products/services has shifted from aspects of use and utilisation to added value in the form of pride. The added value of a product/service is closely aligned with consumer preferences. This added value continues to undergo modifications and refinement as institutions compete to increase their potential consumer base, making effective communication of added value crucial for business success (Royhan & Rum, 2022).

Currently, the market's judgment on the branding and reputation of an institution/company depends on people's perceptions. Knowledge of a brand and its reputation is essential and complex, as branding and reputation can strategically influence people's preferences. This is why the competition to build, manage, and maintain branding and reputation is very important, especially for marketers (businesses). The education sector has a strategic role in educating the nation's future. Its strategic role can be seen in the progress of a nation, measured by the educational level of its citizens. In line with the objectives of education, the use of branding and reputation becomes strategic in driving the marketing of educational services and in raising public awareness of the positioning of academic institutions by school management. In carrying out educational activities, schools of both public and private status significantly contribute to shaping the nation's life, including an Islamic school. Therefore, building a strong brand and reputation in public services is essential to winning the competition, as people tend to purchase products and services from companies with good reputations (Ratnasari & Suradika, 2020).

Branding and reputation in non-profit institutions are also essential, just as they are in business institutions. Similarly, in the modern education sector, facing business competition, managers must possess charisma, managerial capabilities, and the acumen to read and understand their environment (Dakir & Fauzi, 2020). In the educational environment, Islamic schools face stiff competition from public schools, private general schools, madrasahs, Islamic boarding schools, and other Islamic schools, which have been established for a long time, as well as those affiliated with Islamic community organisations. The numerous Islamic schools present in society have created increasingly fierce competition, making it easy for the community to switch school choices if the management can no longer satisfy the needs and desires of prospective students and parents. The current impact is that the challenges for Islamic schools are becoming increasingly stringent,

requiring a positive image, branding, and reputation of the institution to enhance public interest in Islamic schools. Branding and reputation are not only identifiers of an institution, but they also hold the potential to promote products/services. Therefore, branding and reputation become crucial for Islamic schools to attract more and higher-quality prospective students, ensuring the long-term sustainability of the institution's mission and goals.

In this research, it should be emphasised that branding and reputation are at the forefront of shaping public perception and communication actions toward the institution as part of its assets. Through various communication actions, the branding of Islamic schools continues to be socialised to the public through multiple media, such as placing advertisements, displaying logos, organising events, creating press releases, managing social media content, outdoor media, and face-to-face interactions or similar activities that ultimately align with the institution's established reputation. Through the communication actions taken, the branding and reputation of Islamic schools continue to be discussed by the community, resulting from the continuous information dissemination carried out by the management of Islamic schools. Related to the branding and reputation communicated to the broader community, as much as possible, it is an effort to enhance the governance of Islamic school communication, thereby improving the public's perception of the school and its services (Hidayatulloh et al., 2023).

In the context of educational marketing, particularly in Islamic-based institutions, public perception plays a crucial role in shaping attitudes, intentions, and actual behaviours towards educational choices for their children. Perception is an initial cognitive construct formed from information, experiences, cultural values, and social representations that the community obtains regarding Islamic schools. The perception of Islamic schools in some segments of society has been that they excel in character education, the integration of religious values, and the exemplary behaviour of teachers. This initial perception will lead to the formation of societal attitudes towards the intention and actual choice to enrol their children in these institutions. This indicates a paradigm shift where Islamic schools are no longer perceived as exclusive to conservative circles but rather as an alternative, holistic education that is relevant to the demands of the times. However, the actual behaviour of society towards Islamic schools does not always align with perceptions and intentions. Several external factors, such as the availability of facilities, education costs, distance, a curriculum considered rigid, or even sectarian stigma, can create barriers between intention and actual behaviour. Some groups in society still hold stereotypical perceptions that Islamic schools are less adaptive to technological advancements and globalisation. On the other hand, the actual success of Islamic school graduates in the workforce, at prestigious universities, and in the entrepreneurial realm has not been systematically documented (Wahyuni, 2018). This is where Islamic educational institutions must enhance their branding and reputation through effective communication strategies that address the social realities of the community, drawing on religious values and highlighting the success of their graduates, transparency in curriculum, and innovative learning approaches.

Strengthening positive perceptions is a strategic step to shape the intentions and actual behaviours of the community towards Islamic schools. Through professional management of branding and reputation, Islamic schools have the opportunity to become the primary choice for communities

seeking an education that balances spirituality and global competence. Such a condition presents both an opportunity and a challenge for the management of Islamic schools to create educational innovations that align with Sharia requirements, technological advancements, global standards, and local wisdom values, thereby supporting a quality, high-achieving, and Islamic-charactered education favoured by the community. To determine the positive impression of the branding and reputation displayed by Islamic schools, it needs to be measured concretely based on figures obtained from a survey of the target audience, so that market competition can be effectively mapped out.

Based on a review of similar literature, most research on branding and reputation in the public sector focuses on higher education, political, and business institutions. At the same time, studies on Islamic schools remain rare, particularly those employing a quantitative approach. Furthermore, research on branding and reputation tends to be studied from the economic dimension of marketing, which shows that branding is part of the marketing mix. However, this article presents research data from the perspective of communication studies, specifically in the field of public relations, which aims to quantitatively explain the phenomenon of whether or not branding and reputation influence public attitudes, impacting the existence of Islamic schools and the establishment of strong ties of "shilaturahmi" as a characteristic of the institution (Saragih et al., 2024).

Based on the background that has been explained, this study aims to identify and explain the influence of Islamic School branding on public attitudes towards the existence of Islamic Educational Institutions, the influence of Islamic School reputation on public attitudes towards the existence of Islamic Educational Institutions and the combined impact of Islamic School branding and reputation on public attitudes towards the existence of Islamic Educational Institutions.

Literature Review

The Hierarchy of Effects Model

According to Lavidge and Steiner (1961), the Hierarchy of Effects Model was created to illustrate the steps that lead advertisers to assume that consumers go through the purchasing process more clearly. The Hierarchy of Effects Model is employed in this research because it illustrates the process of how information exposure works, assuming that consumers undergo a series of sequential processes, from awareness of a product to taking action (i.e., purchase) (Belch & Belch, 2018). This model assumes that the branding and reputation 'owned' by the company are communicated linearly from the institution/company to the consumer. However, the potential use of this model may sometimes require simultaneous steps. According to Robert Lavidge and Grey Steiner, the Hierarchy of Effects Model is one of the consumer behaviour models that provides a general perspective for analysing the impact of communication, including responses and attitudes toward the message conveyed by the producer (communicator) (Lavidge & Steiner, 1961). The Hierarchy of Effects Model is a concept that describes the process experienced by consumers or audiences when interacting with a marketing message, from the awareness stage to the final action stage.

The hierarchy of effects model illustrates how branding and reputation function; this model assumes that the target audience undergoes a series of sequential processes, from awareness of a product to taking action, forming an attitude, or exhibiting behaviour. This model's basic premise is that communication effects occur periodically. Branding communication may not directly cause a response (such as purchase/use); instead, a series of impacts must occur gradually, where each stage must be fulfilled before the target audience can progress to the next stage in a hierarchy (Pramudita & Nurfebiaraning, 2017).

In the context of branding and the reputation of Islamic schools, this model can be applied to understand how schools develop relationships with parents, students, and the broader community, and how perceptions of branding change with exposure to various messages conveyed by school management. Through the Model Hierarchy of Effects, it is certainly possible to measure the direction of community attitudes and/or behaviours (Y) towards Islamic schools based on the branding (X1) and reputation (X2) dimensions possessed by the Islamic schools.

Branding

Branding plays a vital role in the relationship between companies and customers, navigating the decision-making process by reducing risk and providing shortcuts for product identification (McMurrian & Washburn, 2008). From the consumer's perspective, branding is associated with consumer perceptions, meaning that branding is considered a cognitive construct in the minds of consumers. It is assumed that strong branding has strong, unique, and beneficial associations in the minds of consumers (Heding et al., 2009). Branding makes a product/service communicated to consumers easier to remember and inspires (Young, 2014). Branding is closely related to public relations activities, serving as the guardian of reputation, communication, image, and corporate identity. Branding can be considered a symbolic manifestation of reputation (Rees, 2020).

Branding is a key issue in product strategy, and fulfilling the promises associated with a brand can help service organisations create customer loyalty (Nyffenegger et al., 2015). Thus, the existence of branding is essential because it can place an organisation's name above its competitors (Pandjaitan et al., 2024). Therefore, in branding, a benefit, service, or feature inherent in a product/service will be attached, which can influence the selection process in the minds of consumers. Therefore, based on the existing literature, this research proposes the following hypothesis:

H1: The stronger the branding, the greater its influence on the community's attitude towards Islamic Schools.

Reputation

Corporate reputation has many facets, with different meanings for various disciplines and perspectives (Pires & Trez, 2018). Some disciplinary perspectives include institutional, financial, environmental, and organisational behaviour theories (Feldman et al., 2014). As a concept, reputation can be perceived as a consequence of business interactions with its environment (Casaló et al., 2008). Reputation is a multidimensional attitude construct that is socially built through a continuous process of communication and perception. It is primarily mediated between the reputation entity and its main constituents through collective judgments based on direct and

indirect experiences of past actions and expectations of future actions (Ingenhoff, 2018). According to Haywood (2005), a company's reputation is formed from the perceptions that arise in the minds of stakeholders observing the company (Haywood, 2005). Thus, a company's reputation can be consciously built by its management (Dvorský et al., 2023). The most effective way to communicate with the community, particularly prospective parents of students at Islamic schools, is through face-to-face interactions, outdoor media, and social media. The three communication media can be routinely utilised by the management of Islamic schools to continuously provide the latest information to various stakeholders, thereby facilitating the formation of the institution's reputation. In this model, reputation is examined to determine whether it can influence public attitudes.

The literature review reveals that the reputation of a company/institution can have a significant impact on business, government, and non-profit institutions, as well as Islamic schools. This article examines the influence of reputation on the community's school selection as a tangible expression of its attitude. Furthermore, studying reputation refers not only to an economic approach but also to organisational/public communication. Finally, relatively few studies have reported on the relationship between the reputation of Islamic schools and public attitudes. Therefore, based on the existing literature, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H2: The stronger the reputation, the greater its influence on the community's attitude towards Islamic Schools.

Attitude

Their beliefs and evaluations determine a person's attitude towards an object. Attitude is also a way of mentally filtering thoughts by someone, and it is characterised by optimism and pessimism. Attitude encompasses feelings, beliefs, and information about positive and negative behaviours regarding the entire range of "attitude objects," whether people or things (Olson & Kendrick, 2008). Various definitions of attitude formulated by most experts include "predisposition" or "tendency," which means there is always a tendency. However, a person's behaviour can be predicted once their attitude is known. Thus, an individual will be inclined to exhibit a specific behaviour when they evaluate it positively. Attitude is the focus of this research. According to Belch & Belch (2018), attitude is essential for business practitioners because, theoretically, it represents an evaluation by consumers of an object (in the form of branding or a company) and encompasses both positive and negative feelings and behavioural tendencies.

Method

Research Design

The design of this research uses quantitative research methods. Quantitative research is a type of research that explains a problem with results that can be generalised. In quantitative research, the depth of data and analysis is unimportant. The research method employed is survey research. Survey research is a research method that uses questionnaires as the data collection instrument. The survey research method conducted is an explanatory survey, which is a research explanation of events or conditions (explanation). This explanation is closely related to the question of what causes or influences the occurrence of an event or condition and the consequences it brings. This research employs multiple path analyses to determine the extent of influence between the tested

variables, as per the predetermined quasi-model. Multiple regression is used to analyse the causal relationship between several independent variables (X) and one dependent variable (\hat{Y}) (Ghozali, 2015).

The hypothesis of this research is formulated as follows: (1) there is a direct positive influence of Islamic school branding on community attitudes, (2) there is a direct positive influence of Islamic school reputation on community attitudes, and (3) there is a direct positive influence of Islamic school branding and reputation. Here is the research framework diagram, which illustrates the influence of Islamic school branding and reputation on community attitudes towards the institution.

H1: Islamic Education Branding statistically significantly influences Community Attitudes towards Islamic Schools.

H2: The reputation of Islamic Education statistically significantly influences the community's attitude towards Islamic Schools.

Figure 1. Research Framework

Data Collection and Sampling

Data collection was conducted by administering a questionnaire to respondents that referred to items or questions related to the branding and reputation of Islamic schools. The questionnaire was administered to respondents to answer questions related to the research variable indicators. To obtain data for this research, the researcher distributed questionnaires to the parents of students at the selected school unit. Other data collection techniques include secondary data in Islamic school documents, scientific journals, the internet, magazines, newspapers, and electronic mass media reports.

The population is the community in the West Java region, specifically the parents of students at Islamic schools from Darul Hikam Bandung City, As Syifa Boarding School Subang Regency, Al Azhar 8 Bekasi City, Ummul Quro Bogor Regency, and Itqan Bandung City. Sampling was conducted using the purposive sampling technique, meaning that the samples were selected because they met the criteria to be included as subjects in the research. The research instrument used is a questionnaire developed by the researcher based on a review of previous literature, which was distributed directly to respondents or through a Google Form link.

Data Analysis

The data processing and analysis method employs quantitative analysis using multiple linear regression to test the data quality regarding the branding and reputation of Islamic schools in relation to the attitudes of student parents, based on questionnaire responses from the respondents. Data quality testing using SPSS software version 2022.

Result

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis, in this case, is a regression equation that consists of two or more independent variables with one dependent variable. The independent variables are Branding (X1) and Reputation (X2), with Public Attitude as the dependent variable (Y).

Table 1. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.039	1.242		1.641	.102
1 Branding (X ₁)	.230	.059	.192	3.888	.000
Reputation (X ₂)	.423	.029	.717	14.480	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Attitudes (Y)

Source: Primary Data, 2024

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that multiple linear regression has similarities in this study, so:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \varepsilon$$

$$Y = 2,039 + 0,230X_1 + 0,423X_2 + \varepsilon$$

From the equation above, it can be interpreted as follows:

1. $\alpha = 2,039$. This value is called a constant, which is the state when the variable Y (Public Attitude) has not yet been influenced by other variables, namely the branding variable (X₁) and reputation (X₂). The community's attitude remains unchanged if the independent variables are absent.
2. $\beta_1X_1 = 0,230$. This value is called the regression coefficient for X₁, which indicates that the branding variable has a positive influence on public attitudes, meaning that every 1-unit increase in the branding variable will affect public decisions by 0.230.
3. $\beta_2X_2 = 0,423$. This value is called the regression coefficient X₂, indicating that the reputation variable has a positive influence on public attitudes, meaning that every one-unit increase in the reputation variable will affect public attitudes by 0.230.

Partial t-test

The t-test aims to determine the influence of each independent and dependent variable (Ghozali, 2015). The t-statistic Test (t-test) determines whether the independent variables have an individual or partial effect on the dependent variable. Where the significance level used is 0.05. If the

significance value is less than the confidence level (0.05), we accept the alternative hypothesis that the independent variables partially affect the dependent variable.

Table 2. Partial t-test Results

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.039	1.242		1.641	.102
1 Branding (X ₁)	.230	.059	.192	3.888	.000
Reputation (X ₂)	.423	.029	.717	14.480	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Attitudes

Source: Data Primer, 2024

Table 3. Explanation of Partial t-Test Results

Variable Relations	T	Sig.	t-tabel	Explain
Branding (X ₁) → Attitudes Public (Y)	3.888	0.000	1.969	Significant
Reputation (X ₂) → Attitudes Public (Y)	14.480	0.000	1.969	Significant

Based on the statistical values in the table above, it can be concluded that:

1. The Branding Variable (X₁) has a t-count value of 3.888, more significant than the t-table value of 1.969, and a significance of 0.00. Because the significance value is less than 0.00 < 0.05, it can be concluded that the branding variable (X₁) has a significant effect on public attitudes (Y); in other words, H₁ is accepted.
2. The Reputation Variable (X₂) has a t-value of 14.480, more significant than the t-table value of 1.969, and a significance level of 0.00. Because the significance value is less than 0.00 < 0.05, it can be concluded that the reputation variable (X₂) has a significant effect on public attitudes (Y); in other words, H₁ is accepted.

Discussion

Branding serves as a strategic communication instrument that shapes public perception of an entity, whether an institution, community, or region. According to Keller (2013), branding creates brand associations and a brand image in the public mind, which then influences the attitudinal response or public attitude toward the object (Keller, 2013). In a social context, branding not only influences consumer behavior but also the construction of social meaning and public trust in the values or identities offered (Bhattacharya & Sen, 2003). When branding is carried out consistently and authentically, the public tends to have a positive attitude because they internalize the messages and values that the brand embodies. A t-value of 3.888 indicates that branding has a fairly strong influence on the formation of public attitudes. That branding efforts designed with appropriate communication strategies, such as visual identity, value narratives, and social activities, can improve perceptions and encourage favorable public attitudes toward the branded entity.

Reputation is the result of the accumulated public perception of an organization's or community's actions, communications, and behavioral consistency over time. According to Fombrun & Van Riel (2018), reputation is formed from public trust in an entity's credibility, integrity, and social responsibility (Fombrun, 2018). The calculated t-value of 14,480, significantly higher than the t-table (1,969), indicates that reputation has a significantly greater influence than branding on public attitudes. Suggests that while branding is important in creating awareness and image, reputation is more potent in shaping trust and loyalty, two key components of public attitudes. Aligns with research by (Yadav et al., 2018), which asserts that a good reputation strengthens positive perceptions and increases public attitude alignment, particularly in the context of social organizations and communities. When a reputation is firmly established, people tend to automatically develop positive attitudes because reputation functions as a heuristic cue. This cognitive guide facilitates attitude decision-making without the need for in-depth evaluation.

An institution's strong branding and reputation can evoke positive emotions from the public towards the institution, especially in Islamic schools. Branding and reputation are two interdependent elements that collectively represent an institution/company. Branding has a significant influence on public attitudes, because it is able to build positive perceptions and shared identity values. While reputation has a more dominant and significant influence on people's attitudes, because reputation is formed from experience, consistency of behavior, and trust that has been built up over a long time. In the era of information technology, branding and reputation have become the key to successfully building trust among stakeholders who access social media. Currently, social media is not just a medium for disseminating information but also serves as a medium for promotion, image building, branding, and reputation of an institution, including Islamic schools. Ultimately, social media plays a significant and inseparable role in today's life (Ngoc et al., 2024).

In the context of Islamic education, public trust is built more through a substantial reputation, including academic credibility, moral integrity of the institution, the quality of graduates, and consistency in applying Islamic values in educational practices. Conceptually, these results support the theory that branding serves as a gateway to public perception, while reputation is shaped by real experiences and consistency in values perceived by the community. This broadens the understanding in Islamic education management literature that external communication strategies, through branding, need to be integrated with internal strategies to strengthen quality and values, creating a sustainable and positive attitude in the community. Islamic schools need to strike a balance between building their image (branding) and maintaining quality and integrity (reputation). Without a strong reputation, branding will be merely a temporary cosmetic measure with no lasting impact on public trust.

Conclusion

Based on the results of research on the influence of branding and reputation on public attitudes towards Islamic schools, improving public perception of Islamic schools can be achieved more effectively by developing an excellent and consistent reputation, supported by a strategic and communicative branding approach. More details can be seen below:

1. Branding positively and significantly impacts the community's attitude towards Islamic schools. This indicates that the parents of the students believe the branding of Islamic schools can create a positive impression of their activities.
2. Reputation positively and significantly impacts the community's attitude towards Islamic schools. This demonstrates that the achievements and credibility of Islamic schools reflect the activities that have the advantage of shaping students' character to become more knowledgeable in the field of knowledge and develop their religious values.

Suggestions for Future Research

Finally, future research is recommended to explore additional factors that may influence the dynamics of branding activities and the reputation of both Islamic and general education institutions, and to examine the long-term effects of these variables on maintaining community loyalty to Islamic schools.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (Kemendikbud-saintek) Fundamental Research Grant year 2024. We would also like to express our gratitude to the DRPM Universitas Padjadjaran, as well as the staff and teachers of the Islamic School in West Java, Indonesia, for their participation.

Reference

- Belch, G. E., & Belch, M. A. (2018). Advertising and Promotion: An Integrated Marketing Communications Perspective. In *Belch: Advertising and Promotion, Sixth Edition* (Sixth). Pearson.
- Bhattacharya, C. B., & Sen, S. (2003). Consumer-company identification: A framework for understanding consumers' relationships with companies. *Journal of Marketing*, 67(2), 76–88. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.67.2.76.18609>
- Casaló, L., Flavián, C., & Guinalú, M. (2008). The role of perceived usability, reputation, satisfaction and consumer familiarity on the website loyalty formation process. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24(2), 325–345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2007.01.017>
- Dakir, & Fauzi, A. (2020). *Quality Management of Integrated Islamic Education* (Mazrur (ed.); 1st ed.). Pustaka Pelajar.
- Dvorský, J., Bednarz, J., & Blajer-Gołębiewska, A. (2023). The impact of corporate reputation and social media engagement on the sustainability of SMEs: Perceptions of top managers and the owners. *Equilibrium. Quarterly Journal of Economics and Economic Policy*, 18(3), 779–811. <https://doi.org/10.24136/eq.2023.025>
- Feldman, P. M., Bahamonde, R. A., & Bellido, I. V. (2014). A new approach for measuring corporate reputation. *RAE Revista de Administracao de Empresas*, 54(1), 53–66. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020140102>
- Fombrun, C. J. (2018). Reputation: Realizing Value from the Corporate Image. In *Harvard Business School Press* (20th ed.). Harvard Business School Press.
- Ghozali, I. (2015). *Non-parametric Statistics: Theory and Applications with IBM SPSS 23* (2nd ed.). Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.

- Haywood, R. (2005). Corporate Reputation, The Brand & The Bottom Line: Powerful Proven Communication Strategies for Maximizing Value. In *Manager: British Journal of Administrative Management* (Third, Issue 51). Kogan Page. <https://www.lib.byu.edu/cgi-bin/remoteauth.pl?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=buh&AN=19562116&site=ehost-live&scope=site>
- Heding, T., Knudtzen, C. F., & Bjerre, M. (2009). Brand Management: Research, Theory and Practice. In *Brand Management: Research, Theory and Practice*. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.
- Hidayatulloh, M. D., Irawan, & Priatna, T. (2023). Science Governance in Islamic Educational Institutions through Laboratory Arrangement. *PANDU: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Dan Pendidikan Umum*, 1(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.59966/pandu.v1i1.8>
- Ingenhoff, D. (2018). Reputation. *The International Encyclopedia of Strategic Communication*, 1(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119010722.iesc0148>
- Keller, K. L. (2013). Strategic Brand Management: Building, Measuring, and Managing Brand Equity. In *Pearson Education Limited* (Fourth). Pearson Education, Inc.
- Keller, K. L., Prameswaran, A. M. ., & Jacob, I. (2015). *Strategic Brand Management: Building, Measuring, and Managing Brand Equity* (Fourth). Pearson India Education Services Pvt. Ltd.
- Keni, Dharmawan, P., & Wilson, N. (2021). The Effect of Corporate Reputation, Brand Satisfaction and Brand Attitude on Customer Loyalty in the Aviation Industry in Indonesia. *DeReMa (Development of Research Management): Jurnal Manajemen*, 16(1), 79–95. <https://doi.org/p://dx.doi.org/10.19166/derema.v16i1.2743>
- Lavidge, R. J., & Steiner, G. A. (1961). A Model for Predictive Measurements of Advertising Effectiveness. *Journal of Marketing*, 25(6), 59. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1248516>
- McMurrian, R., & Washburn, J. H. (2008). Branding: A Social Contract between a Business and Its Customer. In T. C. Melewar & E. Karaosmanoglu (Eds.), *Contemporary Thoughts on Corporate Branding and Corporate Identity Management* (pp. 5–22). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Ngoc, N., Vy, T., Nguyen, T., Chau, N., Tien, D. H., & Khang, N. T. (2024). Building personal branding from the reality of University students using dating apps. *PRofesi Humas*, 9(1), 67–89. <https://doi.org/10.24198/prh.v9i1.54982>
- Nyffenegger, B., Krohmer, H., Hoyer, W. D., & Malaer, L. (2015). Service Brand Relationship Quality: Hot or Cold? *Journal of Service Research*, 18(1), 90–106. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670514547580>
- Olson, M. A., & Kendrick, R. V. (2008). Origins of Attitudes. In W. D. Crano & R. Prislin (Eds.), *Attitudes and Attitude Change* (pp. 111–130). Psychology Press. <http://scioteca.caf.com/bitstream/handle/123456789/1091/RED2017-Eng-8ene.pdf?sequence=12&isAllowed=y%0Ahttp://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.regsciurbeco.2008.06.005%0Ahttps://www.researchgate.net/publication/305320484>
- Pandjaitan, R. H., Ganiem, L. M., & Hereyah, Y. (2024). Organizational Communication Competencies and the 4C Model for Branding and Building Reputation Through Social Media. *Jurnal Pelayanan Dan Pengabdian Masyarakat Indonesia*, 3(1), 75–90.
- Pramudita, G., & Nurfebriaraning, S. (2017). Analysis of Spotify Users' Attitudes towards Spotify Premium Ads Based on the Hierarchy of Effect Model. *E-Proceeding of Management*, 4(3), 3232–3238. <https://openlibrarypublications.telkomuniversity.ac.id/index.php/management/article/view/5>

085

- Ratnasari, L., & Suradika, A. (2020). Building the Reputation of Islamic Schools Among Muslim Middle Classes. *Perspektif Komunikasi: Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi Politik Dan Komunikasi Bisnis*, 4(1), 18. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.24853/pk.4.1.18-29>
- Rees, S. (2020). *Public Relations, Branding and Authenticity: Brand Communications in the Digital Age* (K. Moloney (ed.)). Routledge Taylor & Francis Group. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429022685>
- Royhan, A., & Rum, M. (2022). Analysis of added value and business model canvas of Madura Jamu UKM. *Agriscience*, 3(2), 443–461. <https://doi.org/10.21107/agriscience.v3i2.15593>
- Saragih, A., Amelia, C., Batubara, I., Sitohang, D. S., Tanjung, W. F., Al-washliyah, U. M. N., Batam, U., Amplas, M., & Islam, N. (2024). Socialization on Avoiding Bullying from an Islamic Religious Perspective at Nabila Islamic School, Batam City. *Bhakti Nagori*, 4, 287–294. https://doi.org//doi.org/10.36378/bhakti_nagori.v4i2.3989
- Soehadi, A. W. (2005). *Effective Branding*. PT Mizan Pustaka.
- Wahyuni, N. Y. (2018). Image Building: Efforts to Build Public Opinion for Islamic Educational Institutions. *Al-Tanzim: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 2(1), 64–79. <https://doi.org/10.33650/al-tanzim.v2i1.249>
- Yadav, R. S., Dash, S. S., Chakraborty, S., & Kumar, M. (2018). Perceived CSR and Corporate Reputation: The Mediating Role of Employee Trust. *Vikalpa: The Journal for Decision Makers*, 43(3), 139–151. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090918794823>
- Young, A. (2014). *Brand Media Strategy: Integratwd Communications Planning In The Digital Era* (2nd ed.). Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137447715>